

INDIA-IRAN HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL RELATIONS: MAPPING THE INDIAN ACADEMIC RESEARCHES ON IRAN

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Abstract:

India and Iran share deep-rooted historical, cultural, and civilisational ties dating back to the Vedic Age, which were strengthened during the Mughal era through language, literature, and trade. Contemporary academic research in India extensively explores this multifaceted relationship, focusing on political, economic and socio-cultural dimensions. Key areas of study include energy cooperation, particularly the Iran-Pakistan-India gas pipeline, trade diversification and the impact of U.S. sanctions on bilateral relations. Indian scholars also examine Iran's regional influence, its role in Afghanistan and the interplay of global geopolitics on Indo-Iranian ties. Additionally, research highlights cultural exchanges, linguistic connections and medieval Persian influences on Indian society. Despite challenges like Western pressures, India maintains strategic engagement with Iran, balancing energy needs with diplomatic constraints. This paper reviews Indian academic contributions, emphasising evolving themes in the post-Cold War era and underscoring Iran's enduring significance in India's foreign policy and scholarly discourse.

Keyword: India-Iran relations, Academic research, Cultural ties, Energy diplomacy, Geopolitics, Historical interactions

Introduction

India and Iran share a long-standing relationship characterised by deep historical, cultural, and economic ties. Since the previous four or five decades, India and Iran have been working through their academic institutions to comprehend better each other's societies, cultures, and

economic links. It is also clear that, in terms of foreign studies, Iran is the most important topic of research among Indian academics and research scholars. During the Cold War, and particularly when the region's globalisation and liberalisation movements began in the early 1990s, Indian universities and research institutions became more interested in understanding the many elements of India-Iran relations through the Area Studies curriculum. Over the years, numerous research studies and analyses have been conducted to understand the multifaceted nature of this relationship, particularly from an Indian perspective.

This paper is solely based on the content analysis of books and research papers published in academic journals. It also covers the Ph.D theses as well as the M.Phil dissertations completed in Indian universities in recent decades. It aims to review the contemporary researches on India-Iran relationship mainly by the Indian scholars. The purpose is to point out various themes and issues that have been taken up by the academics and researchers for the last few decades in Indian universities and research centers. In a way, this will be a survey type study focusing on how the relationship between India and Iran has been observed by the scholars in India.

India and Iran: A Brief Historical Account

The historical and cultural relationship between India and Iran is very old and it is said that it started during the Vedic Age. The people of these two countries trace their origin from the same family. 'The historical and cultural ties between India and Iran are one of the most ancient of its kind in the world. Indo-Iranian relations were initiated during the Vedic Age. Both the Indians and Iranians are called Aryans so it can be said that they are like brothers who come from the same parent'(Ahmad, 2001) . The relationship between the two countries developed significantly during the Sassanian period.

The relationship flourished on a greater pace during the Mughal rule in India because of several reasons. Important of them are the ruling Mughals and the importance of the Persian language as the official language of India at that time. 'In the reign of Akbar, many Sanskrit texts were translated into Persian. The Ramayana and the Mahabharata, the Amarakosa and other classical works of literature were translated into Persian. Dara Shikoh's translation of the 'Upanishads' into Persian

in 1657 was a unique event in the history of Persian contribution to Indian literature (Ahmad, 2001).

In post-independent India, the cultural and political relations between the two countries have reached on its zenith with the exchange of official visits and visits carried out by the poets and writers. With the visits of Mohammad Reza Shah to India first time in 1956 and then in 1969 and those of Jawahar Lal Nehru, Dr. S. Radhakrishnan, Indira Gandhi and Fakhruddin Ali Ahmad to Iran placed the Indo-Iran political and cultural relations on a very firm footing.

It is interesting to note that Indians and particularly Indian Muslims, have always given importance to know about Iran, its culture and civilisation throughout the ages. The reason is the arrival of Islam to India. All the Islamic seminaries in India had taken keen interest in learning and teaching the Persian language and they developed the teaching materials in the Persian language as far as learning about Islam is concerned. Even today, the Persian language is being taught in every Islamic seminary and modern institutions of learning. India has produced a number of scholars of the Persian language and literature.

Carrying forward the tradition, scholars and researchers of contemporary India are engaged in studying Iran, its society, and its culture. The strong bilateral economic relations are compelling the scholars to study in a broader way as far as Iran is concerned. The scholars are taking keen interest in the internal and external affairs of Iran in the shadow of western sanctions on it. They have covered almost all the themes of Iranian society and government in their studies. In the coming pages, an effort is being made to understand how the Indian scholars are looking at the bilateral relations as well as Iranian affairs in their studies.

Indo-Iran Historical Relations

Indo-relations are at once the oldest and the newest in human history; dating back to time immemorial, they have been most fruitful for human progress ever since they were established. They are based more on the complementarity of economic needs and personal services than merely or exclusively on the identity of political views and social objectives.

Tracing the old relationship between the two countries, a Ph.D thesis titled '*Comparative Study of Vedas and Ancient Iran Worship*' says that

in the beginning of the period of migration some group of Indo- Iranian people migrated to Iran and some other people came to the middle Asia. This group after passing from crossing of North- Western of Hindukush Mountains arrived to “Sapta- Sindhu land” namely “Seven Rivers land” in Punjab. The people who dwell in India were called “Āryan” and they who came to the Iranian Plateau were called “Ariyān” or “Aeryan”. Both of them mean “noble” as the name of Iran has been derived from this root.

It is evident that the inhabitants of Iran and India in spite of having one origin, they were gradually transformed in the new environment and generated two different civilisations from the basis of ancient civilisation of Asia. Both of them worship the nature elements, because of their primary civilisation. They sang to worship of the manifestation of the nature. Indian Mantras have retained in the form of Veda books which are knowledge books and Iranian Gāthā which are base of Avesta, has been sung in description of ancient Iranian Gods (Moghaddam, 2009).

Observing Iran-India historical interactions, particularly in the twenty-first century, has led to the development of the notion that the two nations’ relations are influenced by several elements at three levels: internal, regional, and international. In this sense, the most important areas of collaboration between India and Iran are historical, cultural, political, security-related, economic, and commercial spheres. Cultural links between India and Iran demonstrate the convergence of Indian and Islamic civilisations. In one sense, because it has the world’s second largest Muslim population after Indonesia, and its national culture has been heavily affected by Islam.

India intends to have relations with Iran which is an influential country in the world of Islam. Bringing the field of ‘South Asian regional studies’ into the universities of the two countries, as well as the constant exchanges of academic elites of Iran and India, are necessities for these countries (Movahed, 2012).

Another major aspect of study at Indian academic institutions is the identification of highs and lows in India’s relations with Iran in the post-Cold War period, as well as an analysis of the current situation. India’s Iran policy, like its overall foreign policy, reflects domestic and external concerns and compulsions. India’s desire to protect its interests and extend its alternatives is understandable. However, refraining from

Iran's nuclear issue and failing to launch the Israeli spy satellite to monitor Iranian land would have been completely within India's interests and foreign expectations (Dietl, 2012).

Indo-Iran ties have been the topic of heated debates and discussions in recent years, notably since 9/11. The expanding Indo-US relations are thought to have harmed Indo-Iran relations. Given the anti-Iranian push in U.S. foreign policy, notably on the nuclear issue, Indian foreign policy faces a difficult problem in maintaining a balanced approach to Iran. The researcher examines the entire range of concerns in Indo-Iran relations, including energy security, military and defence collaboration, the Iranian nuclear program, terrorism, commerce, and political, economic, and cultural relationships (Alam, 2011).

According to a research paper, India and Iran commonly highlight their civilisational, cultural and historical links, which the two countries held together for more than a millennium. Following India's independence, both countries maintained strong bilateral connections, overcoming obstacles such as Cold war politics and Iran's relationship with Pakistan. Iran and India have warm and cemented connections, which have resulted in greater regional stability (Rizvi, 2011).

Another researcher brings out the U.S. factor in India-Iran bilateral relations and says that it is also noteworthy that India's ties with Iran were also irritable due to India-U.S. relationship. Several analysts claim that the United States is influencing India's Iran policy. The Iran-Pakistan-India (IPI) pipeline, India's votes against Iran at the International Atomic Energy Agency, and the Reserve Bank of India's December 2010 guidelines, which halted oil payments to Iran through the Asian Clearing Union, are three examples of how the U.S. is said to have influenced Indian policy (Purushothaman, 2012).

Indo-Iran Bilateral Relations and the External Factors

While tracing cultural and commercial relations, one research investigates how Indian and Iranian traders used not just land routes to transport their merchandise, but also the Arabian Sea and the Persian Gulf for continuous trading activity. Before sailing to China via Ceylon, Persian ships anchored at Thana, Surat, Calicut, and Quilon. The situation of Iran in the line of the Silk Road between China and India with the Mediterranean region was very important (Rahimy, 2011).

For example, an M.Phil dissertation titled '*Politics of Pipeline: Comparative Study of Iran-Pakistan-India and Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan Pipeline Projects*' shows that in the changing world of the hydrocarbon market, pipelines are emerging as a choice of transporting system of the energy for both consumers and producers. Two factors have largely contributed towards the acceptability of the pipelines. Firstly, it is a cheaper means of transport. Secondly, it ensures certainty to both producers and consumers in the period. The technological advances in the pipelines have made it to expand to those areas which were inaccessible earlier and thus expand its profile (Kumari, 2006).

A book chapter deals with the economic relations after 1990s. He says that 'Though oil and gas related products constitute the bulk of economic transaction between India and Iran, there is a growing realisation on part of both the countries to diversify their trade and commercial relations in non- oil sector. Author's geo- economic analyses explore the pattern of growing trade and economic relations between the two countries since early 1990s. Both Iran and India are moving ahead to the de- regulation of their economies and both are visualising economic relations beyond the traditional merchandise exports and imports to the emerging opportunities for private investment in each other's potential markets (Khan, 2003).

Another research takes a dig into a holistic view of economic relations between the two nations. He writes 'India adopted policy with regards to Iran for promoting close economic and commercial relations, bilateral agreements coordination of actions and in particular in intra-governmental Joint Commission, working of the technical assistance programme geared to the possibilities of utilising the maximum of India's technical advancement, extending support for economic collaboration and cooperation at regional and international level, securing joint ventures, joint- project, consultancy services projects, soft loans etc. India's relations with Iran grew more important during 1990s (Iqbal, 2014).

Another article examines Iranian-Indian ties, with a focus on energy, both historically and today. It will investigate the state of Iran's energy industry in light of US-imposed sanctions on the Islamic Republic and Iran's threat to close the Strait of Hormuz to shipping. It will examine what this means for Iran's position in the worldwide oil and gas market,

as well as the implications for greater India-Iran relations, considering that energy is a key component of their bilateral ties(Dadwal, 2012). It also investigates the justification for Iran, Pakistan, and India joining into a trade agreement to meet their economic, political, and strategic interests, as well as the restrictions and problems that continue to prevent such an agreement from reaching its full potential. Using the gas pipeline project as an example, the challenges of energy security (as the independent variable) and economic interdependence (as the dependent variable) illustrate the significance of collaboration among these countries (Sahay & Roshandel, 2010).

Iran, as an important player in the hydrocarbon sector, presents both an opportunity and a challenge to India. While Iran's hydrocarbons may help to meet India's growing need for oil and natural gas and contribute to its energy security, its readiness to expand its energy links with Iran beyond merely commercial transactions coincided with its intention to negotiate a civil nuclear agreement with the U.S. Furthermore, some of the two countries' energy deals have stopped due to price conflicts and technological issues, while others have come under international attention and scrutiny. While international sanctions against Iran limit India's capacity to develop its energy relations with Iran, maintaining the status quo has certain economic and political benefits. Hence, India is not yet ready to abandon Iran for the U.S. (Kumaraswamy, 2013).

Another paper investigates the U.S. factor in energy sector. The author says that 'the present attempt of the U.S. to dominate over the supply of energy resources, particularly gas is the continuation of the same story or trend and thus not a new phenomenon. However, it is hoped that all the three countries involved in the project would not allow the extraneous consideration to impact upon the project. Since overwhelming stakes spanning from energy, trade to security issues are involved, it is therefore imperative for Iran and India to resist the U.S. pressure and successfully accomplish the completion of the project. This would create interdependence and inter- linkages among the countries of the region and would contribute greatly towards the economic development and prosperity of the region. The profit is very significant as a factor to improve Indo- Iran relation. Given the potential and vitality of the project, it is hoped that both the countries would make every possible effort to implement project'(Azmi, 2014)

The hydrocarbon relation of India with Iran is the challenging issue in world geopolitics. Another scholar talks on the same issue and says that 'both countries could benefit from the proposed \$5 billion Iran, Pakistan, India gas pipeline project. Iran is the potential gateway to Afghanistan, Central Asia and Europe for India. Regional cooperation in the form of India-Iran and India- Pakistan collaboration can potentially influence bilateral relationships between the countries on key issues and conflicts as well as national security. Geo- economic relations through natural gas trade between India, Iran, and Pakistan challenges the political, historical and strategic realities of the Middle East and South Asia. The hydrocarbon geo- economic relation between India and Iran shall strengthen geopolitics in West and South Asia. Regional cooperation through India – Pakistan collaboration, alongside India- Iran and Iran – Pakistan collaboration can potentially influence bilateral relationships between the countries on key issues and conflicts as well as national security. The exportation of natural gas from Iran to India through Pakistan is a venture which may change the face of regional politics in south Asia. Besides, becoming a key factor in India's energy security calculus, Iran has emerged as India's potential gateway to Afghanistan, Central Asia and Europe' (Alam, 2008)

Indo-Iran Socio-Cultural Relations

Although the primary focus of contemporary Indian university researchers is on the social science framework dealing with international relations from an economic and geostrategic perspective, researchers have recently paid attention to engaging their studies from sociolinguistic and cultural perspectives. The cultural, scientific, economic, religious, and political ties that existed between Iran, Rome, and India throughout the Sassanian era. In the domains of literature, music, dance, medicine, science, philosophy, and religion, the Iranians were inspired by Indian culture and civilisation throughout the Sassanian period. For example, one study examines the Indo-Iranian interaction with a focus on the Sassanid era, drawing on numerous Persian and Indian primary and secondary sources. Throughout history, Iranians and Indians have had constant contact.

One Doctoral thesis focusses on two ritualistic folk art forms: the Iranian *Ta'ziyeh* and the Indian *Mudiyettu*. This combines two distinct types of performances as well as two distinct ritual traditions. In a broader

thematic comparison, the researchers looked at the underlying commonalities between the mythologies and histories that are expressed through ritual performance.

With regard to the cultural and social engumens, the researchers have looked at the divergences and similarities between the two ritual performances. In a more thematic comparison, one researcher looked at the underlying similarities between the legends and histories that find their expressions in the performance of the rituals (Lichaei, 2010).

Researchers are also pointing out the prospects for understanding the two great civilisations of India and Iran. In one study, researchers discuss how the Iranian civil law system of obligation and the Indian Common Law systems of torts deal with many legal issues in the same way, but there are also significant differences between these two legal systems in terms of legal structure, classification, fundamental concepts, and terminology (Dezfuli, 2012).

Another scholar takes up the issue of sexuality and says that ‘sexuality is constructed in and through particular historical, cultural and special contexts; the associated sphere is permeable and constraining with each other. Therefore, any socio- political, economic cultural changes would mark evident changes in sexuality. Hence, like any other phenomena, sexuality is also part of history and history is part of sexuality. This work attempts to conceive and theorise sexuality and to study and comprehend the term taking cues from Iranian situation. As the attempt here is to comprehend and conceive the term sexuality in the context of Iranian society (Sivakeerthi, 2013).

Impact of Iranian culture during medieval period and Iranian Diaspora in India has also attracted the attention of researchers. According to an article, ‘Portuguese sixteenth-century sources contain valuable information on neighbouring countries in India, particularly Goa. There are many intriguing items, particularly on the Sultanate of Bijapur, with less on Ahmednagar, and only scattered notes on the other Deccan sultanates, who had little relations with the Portuguese. They attest to the presence of many Iranians in both the sultanates’ armed forces and civil administrations. Some Portuguese chroniclers were very sensitive to social divisions and power dynamics, whereas others just recorded anecdotes. Nonetheless, they contain the names of numerous people, as well as information about their lives, which frequently supplement those

provided by Indo-Persian writers; when compared to the latter, they can be used by researchers with good results. The article also attempts to explain why Iranians were more numerous and important in the Deccan than in other areas of Moslem India, such as Gujarat. It will be followed by a second one addressing Iranians in maritime India and the Indian Ocean' (Thomaz, 2014).

Indo-Iran Relationship and the World

The rapidly changing international environment, as well as the related strategic elements, have served as catalysts for the two countries to realign their foreign policy towards one another. However, much more work is needed to provide economic and political backing for a long-term strategic direction in the bilateral partnership. This article aims to capture the evolving direction of India's relations with West Asia in general, and Iran in particular. The article also covers the political, economic, cultural, and security aspects of India's expanding relationship with Iran (Rizvi, 2011).

India's relationship with Iran has been strained due to external reasons. This article examines Pakistan's position in the relationship, including its religious identity, geopolitical approach to Afghanistan, and energy links with the three countries. The article discusses Pakistan's role in the India-Iran strategic partnership and how Afghanistan serves as the glue for India-Iran relations, despite the cracks in their ongoing connection. The paper finishes with a summary of this unique triangle connection, appraising the participants' overall interests (Ramana, 2012).

Iran and Iraq are the foremost states in West Asian region which are the two most populous countries and occupy strategic positions on the world map. The two countries possess two thirds of the global reserves of petroleum on which Western countries depend a great deal to feed up their economy. In his research he discussed the turbulent period in the history of West Asia. The Iranian Revolution of 1979 was an unprecedented event created ripples across the region (Mirza, 2014).

After analysing U.S. policy towards Iran, another research scholar concludes that U.S. – Iran, which were once very close partner and in alliance, completely broken ever since 1979. The U.S. made every effort to contain and strangulate Iran. However, the animosity and conflict became much sharper in the aftermath of the 9/11. The relationship

became much more complex due to Israel which has been pressurising the U.S. to use force and coercion to check Iran alleged nuclear programme. Israel enjoys a very special relationship and has capability to influence the U.S. policy towards West Asian and Iran (Katiyar, 2015).

In view of the U.S. and European sanctions on Iran on its nuclear programme, it has always been a difficult task for Indian to maintain its relationship with Tehran. the authors argue that 'in recent years, Iran has come to acquire a significant place in the West Asian region with the ability to influence regional politics. For India, relations with Iran are vital. In the changed strategic environment, both India and Iran have been working towards improving their bilateral relations. However, there are several challenges, especially for India, in this regard. If the Iran-U.S. confrontation intensifies, for example, India may find it difficult to pursue a smooth relationship with Iran. This article looks at various facets of India-Iran relations and examines the opportunities and challenges that lie ahead' (Lele & Roy, 2011).

Conclusion

Cultural links between India and Iran demonstrate the convergence of Indian and Islamic civilisations. India aims to establish relations with Iran, a powerful country in the globe. The last quarter of the twelfth century saw a significant increase in the number of academic works and researches conducted in Indian universities and research centres, as well as in political science and history departments of Indian universities. The current focus on Indo-Iranian ties has emerged in academic studies mostly after the end of the Cold War.

The researchers and academics in India have covered almost all the angles of India-Iran relationship. Major focus areas are evident in the contemporary researches and they are trade, commerce, oil and natural gas and cultural relations in addition with political relations. Iran-India relations, particularly since the beginning of the century, have been influenced by several kinds of domestic, regional, and international variables, and researchers have given close attention to these issues.

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